

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Wild species of *Oryza* with resistance to rice blast (BI)

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The 24 wild species of genus *Oryza* are an important source of useful genes for tolerance for and resistance to adverse abiotic and biotic stresses. We evaluated 73 accessions representing 13 wild species for resistance to BI, using both artificial and natural inoculation methods. Seeds of wild species (see table) were obtained from the International Rice Germplasm Center at IRRI. Pregerminated seeds were sown in 4-inch pots in upland soil in a glasshouse. IR36 and IR50 served as controls in all, and CO 39 in some, experiments. *O. sativa* cultivars were planted later than wild species in some cases to compensate for their varying growth rates.

At about the three-leaf stage, at least four seedlings of each accession were inoculated artificially by spraying with a conidial suspension (10^5 cells/ml) of *Magnaporthe grisea* isolate P06-6. For natural inoculation, pots of seedlings were placed in the midst of infected spreader cultivars of *O. sativa* in the International Rice Research Institute Blast Nursery, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. After 5-7 d incubation, leaves were examined for lesions and scored using a scale that differentiates among six reaction levels, where 0 = immune, 1 and 3 = resistant, 5 = intermediate, 7 = susceptible, and 9 = highly susceptible (see table).

Of the 11 wild species tested in both artificial and natural conditions, at least one of six species appeared resistant both to BI isolate P06-6 and inoculum in the BI nursery. Accessions of *O. alta*, *O. barthii*, *O. latifolia*, *O. perennis*, and *O. rufipogon* were found susceptible to isolate P06-6 but resistant in the BI

Disease reaction of *Oryza* species to BI.*

Species	Accession	Inoculation method		Species	Accession	Inoculation method	
		Spraying method (isolate P06-6)	Blast nursery			Spraying method (isolate P06-6)	Blast nursery
<i>O. alta</i>	101395	S	R		103878	R	R
<i>O. australiensis</i>	100882	S	S		103880	R	R
	103318	S	NA		103882	R	R
<i>O. barthii</i>	101243	R	NA		104670	R	R
	101827	S	S		104674	R	R
	101937	R	R		104676	R	R
	104304	S	R		104677	R	R
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101232	R	R		105123	R	R
					105124	R	R
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	101405	R	R		105125	R	R
					105126	R	R
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100914	S	R		105131	R	R
	105141	R	NA		105132	R	R
	105142	R	NA		105253	R	R
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	103886	S	S		105307	R	R
<i>O. minuta</i>	101079	R	R	<i>O. nivara</i>	100899	S	S
	101080	R	R		101193	S	S
	101081	R	R		101524	R	R
	101083	R	R		101973	R	R and S
	101086	R	R		103422	R and S	R and S
	101092	R	R		103826	R	R
	101094	R	R		103839	R	NA
	101099	R	R		104443	R	R
	101101	R	R	<i>O. officinalis</i>	105220	R	NA
	101123	R	R	<i>O. perennis</i>	100692	R	R
	101124	R	R		103817	R	R and S
	101125	R	R		103848	R	R
	101126	R	R		104453	S	R
	101128	R	R		104764	S	R
	101132	R	R		104823	S	S
	101133	R	R	<i>O. ridleyi</i>	100877	R and S	NA
	101134	R	R	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	100211	R	S
	101141	R	R		100923	S	S
	101181	R	R		103305	S	S
	101187	R	R		103817	S	R
	101386	R	R		104413	S	S
	103874	R	R		104479	R	R
	103876	R	R				

*R = resistant reaction (scores of 0, 1, 3), R and S = heterogeneous reaction (all scores), S = susceptible reaction (scores of 7, 9), NA = data not available or not shown due to insufficient number of plants. Sample size: at least four plants per accession.

nursery exposure. *O. rufipogon* also contained an accession resistant to isolate P06-6 but susceptible to BI nursery isolates. Some accessions of *O. nivara*, *O. perennis*, and *O. ridleyi* appeared to be heterogeneous for resistance, as suggested by both resistant and susceptible plants

being found in the same seed lot.

All 38 accessions of *O. minuta* were highly resistant or immune to both artificial and natural inocula. These results indicate that *O. minuta* and *O. brachyantha* are important sources of resistance to BI. ■